

NEWSLETTER

January 2024

FEEDACTIV

UNIVERSITATEA DE STINTE AGRICOLE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA CLUJ NAPOCA (USAMV) is proud to be the Coordinator of the FEEDACTIV Project. FEEDACTIV started in January of 2023 and is here to bring innovative solutions to the need for innovative fish feed supplements. FEEDACTIV consortium is comprised of partners of a vast spectrum of interdisciplinary knowledge and expertise (4 Research, Technology and Development organisations and 4 Small and Medium-sized Enterprises) from 3 European countries, that exchange skills and knowledge.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101086261

FEEDACTIV ambition is to develop innovative aquaculture feed supplements based on natural bioactive compounds that boost the immune system and exhibit antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. In order to accomplish this, during FEEDACTIV project life time, 314 secondment months will be implemented, at least 27 researchers will be trained in the scientific area of extraction of bioactive compounds and innovative fish feed will be formulated with subsequent evaluation of their effect in large scale aquaculture and implementation of overall sustainability assessment.

In the imminent future, FEEDACTIV will organise workshops and experience exchange events to bring the project's outcomes to a wider audience. FEEDACTIV ultimately aspires to promote young entrepreneurship, self-employment and innovation in the fish feed value chain, to meet EU sustainability goals.

Prof. Dr. Dan Cristian Vodnar, Vice-Rector for Research at USAMVCN, FEEDACTIV coordinator

PARTNERS

“USAMVCN is a multidisciplinary research group comprised of scientists with backgrounds in chemical engineering, food engineering, process technology, and biochemistry. In the FEEDACTIV project, USAMVCN conducts the characterization, evaluation and selection of algae and plants with antioxidant and antimicrobial action, in order to recover the bioactive ingredients and applies the quality control of the extracts. Moreover, USAMVCN takes care of the management and coordination of the project.” (<https://www.usamvcluj.ro/en/>)

“Our vision in DIGNITY is to bring feasible solutions in a sustainable industrial landscape. In FEEDACTIV, DIGNITY will work on the indication of hotspots regarding energy and material flows in extraction and encapsulation processes via LCA analysis, the implementation of sustainability assessment of final products and the determination of commercial potential of final products. Moreover, DIGNITY organizes the dissemination and communication activities of the project.” (<https://dignity.com.gr/>)

“ZONOMI is a company located in Greece, with more than 35 years experience in fish feed production for mediterranean fish species as well as for other freshwater fish species. The vision of the company is the production of high quality and sustainable fish feed covering all life stages for the aquaculture sector. In FEEDACTIV, ZONOMI will provide infrastructure and knowledge to run pilot trials of functional fish feed production.” (<https://www.zoonomi.gr/en/>)

“Our role in the project is to evaluate in vitro the antibacterial activity of the selected extracts against important marine bacterial pathogens and assess the impact of the new enriched fish feed on fish performance by administering them to experimental animals.” (<https://www.aegean.edu/>)

“Our role in the project is the evaluation of the effect of innovative feed products during commercial operation aquaculture conditions on growth, survival and parasitic load. Particularly, University of Messina will conduct health monitoring activity, feed effects and growth performance evaluation.” (<https://international.unime.it/>)

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“PISCICOLA SA, is a specialized fish farm with a current production capacity of approximately 350 tonnes annually. Our role in FEEDACTIV involves applying new diets in actual aquaculture conditions, monitoring zootechnical parameters, and tracking variations in daily mortality.” (<https://www.livrarepeste.ro/>)

“The Laboratory of Process Analysis and Design (LPAD) at the School of Chemical Engineering, NTUA, comprises 2 Professors, 3 permanent researchers, 8 post-doctoral researchers, 8 PhD candidates, and 10 undergraduate students. In the FEEDACTIV project, our role involves optimizing bioactive compounds encapsulation and developing stable formulations for enhanced bioavailability in farmed fish feed.” (<https://www.ntua.gr/en/>)

“ PANITTICA ITALIA SOCIETA AGRICOLA SRL, specializing in sea bass and sea bream fish farming, plays a key role in FEEDACTIV by implementing new diets in real aquaculture settings and closely monitoring zootechnical parameters. Our participation aims to acquire valuable knowledge in innovative fish diet practices, aligning with market demands and establishing a competitive edge.” (<https://www.panitticaitalia.it/>)

Project Facts

8

Partners

3

European Countries

314

Secondment months

48

Months

14

Deliverables

8

Work packages

4

Milestones

1,4M

€ EU Contribution

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WHAT FEEDACTIV SECONDED RESEARCHERS TELL US ABOUT THEIR EXPERIENCE OUR FEEDACTIV SECONDED RESEARCHERS SHARE THEIR THOUGHTS

Hello, my name is Anna and I'm thankful that FEEDACTIV and Marie Curie RISE action gave me the opportunity to expand my knowledge on fish production and improve my professional skills.

It's Vassilis Bakopoulos, a professor at the University of Aegean, Lesvos, Greece. We are partners of a project named FEEDACTIV, funded by the Marie Curie Action of Staff Exchange. We would like to express our enthusiasm for the exchange of knowledge and the cooperation between us and the esteemed companies and other universities around Europe.

Hi, I am Diana Plamada, a PhD student at the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine. And thanks to FEEDACTIV and Marie Curie RISE action, I expanded my knowledge on fish feed additives production, improving my professional skills.

Hello, I am Alexandra Mari PhD candidate at National Technical University of Athens. I am currently working on the FEEDACTIV project here in Romania and I am so glad because I am living in a new country, meeting new people and learning new things about aquaculture, feed and farmed fish.

Hi. I'm Theodosios Dimitriadis, I'm a fish pathologist and I'm seconded from the National Technical University of Athens here in Panittica in Italy. I wanted to thank FEEDACTIV for giving me the opportunity to expand both my network and evolve my career skills in the field of aquaculture.

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I am Fulvia Romito and I am a veterinarian at Panittica Italia. I want to thank FEEDACTIV Project and Marie Curie because I had the opportunity to evolve my career and get in touch with the esteemed universities and companies

Hi, I'm Kristian Riolo, PhD from the University of Messina. Thanks to FEEDACTIV and Marie Curie RISE action I improved my professional skills by increasing my knowledge in the aquaculture sector, in the fish breeding and in formulation of feed for aquaculture.

Hello, my name is Sergio Famulari, Ph.D. from the University of Messina. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the FEEDACTIV project and Marie Curie RISE Action for giving me the opportunity to improve my professional skills in the field of aquaculture and feed production. I have also had the chance to live in European cities I did not know before and to meet wonderful people who have always made me feel at home.

Hello, I'm Dr. Claudio Gervasi, a PhD from the University of Messina. I extend my gratitude to FEEDACTIV and the Marie Curie RISE initiative for enabling me to enhance my expertise in freshwater fish management. I'm excited about the emerging collaboration between the academic community and European enterprises, marking a crucial milestone in bridging academia and industry.

Hello, I'm Mariachiara Costanzo, a Ph.D. student at the University of Messina. Currently, I'm immersed in the exciting environment of the FEEDACTIV Project in Greece. I feel truly grateful for this invaluable opportunity as it allows me to enhance my expertise in fish feed additives production and refine my professional skills within the dynamic realm of aquaculture.

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Dissemination Material

All the necessary promotional material needed for the dissemination activities of the FEEDACTIV project has been designed, namely:

- 1.a brochure
- 2.a bookmark
- 3.a leaflet
- 4.a roll-up/poster

The leaflet was created in English and translated by the partners to their native languages (Greek, Romanian).

PARTNERS

CONTACT US

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Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origins.

HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01

HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01
Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origins.

FEEDACTIV AT A GLANCE

To improve the productivity of European Aquaculture with environmental, economic, and social acceptance

To cover the consumer's demand for safe, chemical free, fresh and high quality products from sustainable fisheries

To create a new and more importantly, sustainable source of natural ingredients that can be integrated at an industrial level within the food supply chain.

8 Partners	3 European Countries	314 Secondment months	48 Months
14 Deliverables	8 Work packages	4 Milestones	1,4M € EU Contribution

FEEDACTIV

FEEDACTIV AT A GLANCE

3 European Countries

8 Partners

8 Work packages

48 Months

14 Deliverables

1,4M € EU Contribution

4 Milestones

314 Secondment months

FEEDACTIV AT A GLANCE

FEEDACTIV focuses on the development of innovative aquaculture feed supplements based on natural bioactive compounds that boost the immune system and exhibit antioxidant and antimicrobial activity.

The project aims to improve the quality of farmed fish species by using bioactive agents from alternative raw materials of plant and marine origin in feed supplements.

To improve the productivity of European Aquaculture with environmental, economic and social acceptance

To cover the consumer's demand for safe, chemical free, fresh and high quality products from sustainable fisheries.

To create a new and more importantly, sustainable source of natural ingredients that can be integrated at an industrial level within the food supply chain.

Workflow

WP 1: Characterization, evaluation and selection of algae and plants with antioxidant and antimicrobial activity - Recovery of bioactive compounds and quality control of the produced extracts

WP 2: Encapsulation of bioactive ingredients with antimicrobial and antioxidant action in order to integrate them into functional fish feed supplements

WP 3: Development of innovative feed products by replacing antibiotics with phytochemicals - Quality control of the produced fish feed

WP 4: Evaluation of the effect of selected bioactive ingredients against common bacterial fish pathogens in vitro and of new enriched fish feed on a semi-pilot scale in simulated conditions of cultivation

WP 5: Evaluation of the effect of innovative functional fish feed products on growth, survival, feed and parasite load in real full-scale aquaculture operation conditions

WP 6: Compliance with ethics requirements

WP 7: Management and Coordination

WP 8: Dissemination and Communication Activities

WP 9: Ethics requirements

HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01
Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origins.

CRITICAL ISSUES

1. The development of technical and scientific knowledge on aquaculture, which will reduce the impact on the environment, dependence on fishmeal and fish oils, enhance sustainable use of aquaculture resources and improve animal welfare.
2. Optimise production of fish products with high nutritional value in terms of volume and quality
3. The interest for increased fertilisability, dictates the incorporation of functional ingredients into fish feed in a stable and bioavailable form.
4. Novel, environmentally friendly techniques are needed for maximum, green recovery of compounds. Production of bioactive agents, is also needed for maximizing bioavailability and controlled release
5. Development of protocols for monitoring fish pathology, zootechnical parameters and variations in daily mortality
6. Model-based process optimization based on quality and safety properties of the fish feed.

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HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01
Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origins.

314 Secondment months to implement 6 research steps

1. Characterization, evaluation and selection of algae and plants with antioxidant and antimicrobial activity - Recovery of bioactive ingredients from selected species and quality control of the extracts
2. Encapsulation of bioactive ingredients with antimicrobial and antioxidant action in order to integrate them into functional fish feed supplements
3. Development of innovative feed products by replacing antibiotics with phytochemicals - Quality control of the produced fish feed
4. Evaluation of the effect of selected bioactive ingredients against common bacterial fish pathogens in vitro and of new enriched fish feed on a semi-pilot scale in simulated conditions of cultivation
5. Evaluation of the effect of innovative functional fish feed products on growth, survival, feed and parasite load in real full-scale aquaculture operation conditions
6. Compliance with ethics requirements.

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HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01
Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origins.

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Find us

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Dissemination actions

You can find various resources related to FEEDACTIV on the Linktree link (<https://linktr.ee/feedactiv>), including the website, Facebook page, LinkedIn page, Twitter page, YouTube Channel and Zenodo repository. Additionally, the link provides direct access to questionnaires like the project impact assessment. It generates analytics and a QR code that redirects users to the Linktree account. Project beneficiaries use this QR code in their dissemination activities, presentations, and printable materials to broaden the project's audience.

To enhance the visibility of FEEDACTIV on social media, a YouTube channel has been established. The channel, known as @FEEDACTIVproject, features a promotional video aimed at informing the public about the project as well as a video about the 1st FEEDACTIV workshop and the presence of the project at the European Researchers' Night. Moving forward, additional videos will be uploaded to provide more engaging and informative content, such as presentations, for those interested in the project.

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1st FEEDACTIV workshop

The 1st FEEDACTIV workshop was successfully held on 29th of September at Cluj-Napoca. Each partner presented their work packages and attendees were able to learn more about the project and ask questions to the work-package leaders. In the workshop poster session, each WP leader presented a poster with the most important results and also delivered a 5 min ppt presentation in order to help attendees understand the scope of the project and the benefits it offers.

FEEDACTIV @ European Researchers' Night

The FEEDACTIV project was presented in the European Researchers' Night, hosted at Cluj-Napoca, Romania, on September 29th. The team of USAMV, presented the FEEDACTIV project with great success since more than 200 persons visited their booth. The audience had the chance to be informed about the innovations of FEEDACTIV project and discuss with young researchers of USAMV team about their experience of staff exchanges and the opportunities that MSCA Actions give to young researchers.

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FEEDACTIV @ European Researchers' Night

The FEEDACTIV project was also presented in the European Researchers' Night, hosted at:

1. Athens, Greece
2. Lesvos, Greece
3. Messina, Italy

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FEEDACTIV @ 22nd International Conference "Life Sciences for Sustainable Development", Cluj-Napoca, Romania

The FEEDACTIV project was widely presented in the 22nd International Conference "Life Sciences for Sustainable Development", Cluj-Napoca, Romania, between 28th– 30th September, 2023 with the following oral and poster presentations:

1. Antibacterial Activity Of *Ulva Lactuca* Against Important Aquaculture Bacterial Strains presented by Sofia Pappou, Ioannis Batjakas, Mihail Angelos Valsamidis, Vasileios Bakopoulos
2. Encapsulation Of Bioactive Ingredients With Antimicrobial And Antioxidant Action In Order To Integrate Them Into Feed Supplements presented by Alexandra Mari, Magda Krokida, Lavinia Florina Călinoiu, Dan Vodnar
3. Designing The Framework For The Environmental Analysis Of The Addition Of Natural Antimicrobial And Antioxidant Agents To The Feed Production Line presented by Anna Moustogianni, Bianca Vodnar, Mihaela Pășcuță, Diana Plamada, Maria Giovanna Piro, Claudio Gervasi, Rosa Falletti, Sergio Famulari, Adrian Ghere And Sofia Papadaki
4. Application Of Green Extraction Techniques For The Recovery Of Bioactive Compounds From Citrus Peels By Foteini Polonyfi, Sofia Papadaki, Bernadette-Emoke Teleky, Lavinia Florina Călinoiu, Theodosios Dimitriadis, Magdalini Krokida And Dan Vodnar

ACHIEVEMENTS

From January 2023 to December 2023, 21 secondments have been completed and 3 were ongoing. The following activities were carried out:

WP3 is focused on agricultural by-products (lemon peel, orange peel, olive leaves, bog bilberry leaves), herbs (rosemary, thyme, garlic), and marine algae (spirulina, chlorella) have been used by USAMV to recover bioactive substances through innovative, green extraction technologies. The source with the best antimicrobial and antioxidant activity will be selected to be used as fish feed supplement.

WP4 focused on enhancing bioavailability, sustaining activity through the digestive system, and improving absorption are key objectives in formulating fish feed additives. The team of NTUA as work package leader has already implemented a thorough literature review on the selection of proper matrices for the encapsulation of targeted bioactive substances.

WP5 assessed the phytobiotics and essential oils with encapsulated lemon peel, orange peel, olive leaves have been formulated in Zoonomi, while focusing on the quality control of the incoming raw materials, extruded feed, labeling and quality control of final products regarding the EU legislation for the production of feed. Data has been collected for life cycle assessment (LCA) for the economic and environmental assessment of innovative fish feed products developed to replace antibiotics with phytobiotics

As for **WP6**, important bacterial strains in aquaculture industry have been selected and in vitro antibacterial testing protocols have been standardized for testing the antibacterial sensitivity of extracts sent to UoA by USAMV and NTUA. Preliminary evaluation of the health status and performance of control fish populations fed with commercial fish feed has been conducted in Pannitica and Piscicola SA facilities.

Lastly, for **WP7** research activities that took place involved the evaluation of health status of fish reared in natural conditions in Piscicola SA and evaluation of feed produced in Zoonomi. Moreover a pilot study is being designed in UNIME to evaluate the feed effects in *C. carpio* juveniles.

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